

MorphoBank Connects

Conference Proceedings

**September 18 & 19,
2025**

Welcome to MorphoBank Connects 2025!

On behalf of the organizing team, thank you for joining the first-ever MorphoBank Connects. This inaugural virtual gathering brings together researchers, educators, curators, students, and data professionals with a shared commitment to open, reproducible morphological research.

Whether you are presenting a project, joining a workshop, or exploring how MorphoBank can support your own work, we hope these sessions provide meaningful insights, spark new collaborations, and inspire innovative uses of morphological data to advance science.

About MorphoBank Connects

MorphoBank Connects 2025 marks the first dedicated community event for MorphoBank users and contributors. The conference is designed not only to showcase the scientific advances and creative applications emerging from MorphoBank projects, but also to build connections among people who care about high-quality, accessible morphological data.

Success for this event is not measured by attendance alone. Each presentation, discussion, and informal exchange contributes to a stronger culture of collaboration, data sharing, and reproducibility in the morphological sciences.

Through this and future gatherings, we aim to:

- Encourage active engagement among MorphoBank users and contributors.
- Inspire best practices in data archiving, accessibility, and citation.
- Promote MorphoBank as a trusted repository that benefits both individual researchers and the broader scientific community.
- Grow a network of advocates who will amplify awareness of MorphoBank's value across disciplines.

Celebrating One Year of MorphoBank Volunteers

In July, MorphoBank marked the first anniversary of its volunteer program, launched with a cohort of volunteers from the American Museum of Natural History (AMNH). Over the past year, our dedicated volunteers have contributed hundreds of phylogenetic matrices. Their work strengthens research reproducibility and exemplifies the power of community-driven science. We are grateful to **Brian Y. Ike, Marisol Manns, P. Cidambi Gopalratnam, Tara Mulvaney, Asli E., Meicen Song, Latimer Kells, and Kate Heim** for their commitment and enthusiasm.

Here's to the next year with our volunteer curators!

Code of Conduct

MorphoBank Connects is dedicated to providing a **welcoming, inclusive, and respectful environment** for all participants. We expect everyone—attendees, speakers, organizers, and volunteers—to contribute to a positive conference experience. Harassment, intimidation, or discrimination in any form will not be tolerated.

By registering, attendees agree to uphold this Code of Conduct. Violation of these guidelines may result in removal from the event.

Expected Behavior:

- Treat all participants with respect, courtesy, and professionalism.
- Foster an environment where diverse ideas, perspectives, and backgrounds are valued.
- Offer constructive feedback; critique ideas, not individuals.
- Be mindful of your words and actions in all spaces, including presentations, workshops, chats, and social media.

If you experience or witness inappropriate behavior, you may report it anonymously or directly by emailing the organizing team at conference@morphobank.org. All reports will be handled with care and confidentiality.

Schedule

Thursday, September 18, 2025 - Presentations

Time (PDT)	Title	Speakers
8:00 am	Welcome	Brooke Long-Fox and Tanya Berardini
8:15 am	Repository of morphological data for deep-sea faunal novelties	Xikun Song
8:30 am	Building a bigger tent: institutional tracking of data publications and maximally FAIR data require rigorous repository metadata standards	Bryan Gee
8:45 am	Making academic publishing Open and FAIR: how MorphoBank aids data reproducibility	Mark Young
9:00 am	Accelerating FAIR Morphological Data Curation with an AI-Empowered Tool	Shreya Jariwala
9:15 am	Quantitative analysis of ophiomicrodermatoglyphics in shed-off skin: a novel taxonomic approach in snake identification	Harij Uddin
9:30 am	Is morphology still relevant to phylogenetic analyses?	Daniel Yudi Miyahara Nakamura
9:45 am	Fluctuating Asymmetry Reveals Species-Specific and Metapopulation Responses to Anthropization in Squamates	Aldo Gomez-Benitez
10:00 am	Keynote	Maureen O'Leary
10:30 am	Volunteer Recognition	Brooke Long-Fox
Adjournment		

Schedule

Friday, September 19, 2025 - Workshop & Project Support

Time (PDT)	Title	Speakers
8:00 am - 9:45 am	MorphoBank Workshop	Brooke Long-Fox and Tanya Berardini
9:45 am	Break	
10:00 am - Noon	Project Support Office Hours	Brooke Long-Fox and Tanya Berardini
Adjournment		

Invited Keynote: History of MorphoBank

Maureen O'Leary, PhD

Dr. Maureen O'Leary is a paleontologist whose research focuses on the origin, evolution, and systematics of mammals, particularly during the Early Cenozoic when many modern mammalian orders first emerged. Her work is field-based, with expeditions spanning West Africa, North America, and a long-term project in the Republic of Mali.

Dr. O'Leary is the founder of MorphoBank, the central repository for peer-reviewed morphological matrices for phylogenetic reconstruction, and served as its director from 2000–2021. MorphoBank is widely used to enable collaborative studies of the Tree of Life using phenotypic data.

Beyond mammals, her publications encompass fish, archosaurs, turtles, plants, trace fossils, and invertebrates. Current projects include monographic descriptions of newly discovered fossils from the Late Cretaceous–Early Paleogene of North America, Africa, and Mongolia, with a focus on integrating fossils into phylogenetic frameworks using cladistic methods. Her past contributions range from anatomical analyses of ungulate ear regions to studies on the terrestrial origins of whales and evidence of gradual evolution in early primates.

Building a bigger tent: institutional tracking of data publications and maximally FAIR data require rigorous repository metadata standards

Bryan M. Gee* ,

University of Texas Libraries, University of Texas at Austin, TX, USA

*bryan.gee@austin.utexas.edu

Keywords: FAIR Principles; discoverability; metadata schemas; DataCite

Best practices around management and sharing of research data are rooted in the FAIR Principles. Translating these principles into practice is often challenging, in part because their necessarily high-level framework allows claims of FAIR data when only minimum standards are met (e.g., a dataset having a DOI). Viewing FAIR as a gradient (FAIRness) rather than as a binary requires both greater commitment to the quality of metadata and data and more expansive concepts of what data access and reuse may look like. Most current efforts around improving the FAIRness of data focus the specific use case of data generated by a researcher that is reused for further research by another researcher. However, other entities in the scholarly ecosystem have a vested interest in research data and represent alternative use case. For example, funders are interested in monitoring compliance with data sharing mandates, and research institutions are interested in communicating the full scope of research outputs. Both use cases require the ability to systematically discover datasets at scales much larger than individual researchers through centralized metadata locations (e.g., the DataCite API) and thus rely on quality metadata to discover data. Quality metadata in turn hinge on repository infrastructure and workflows. I will discuss work at the University of Texas at Austin to discover affiliated research datasets and will demonstrate how widespread heterogeneity in repository metadata practices produce extensive gaps in findability. I will then highlight actionable steps that repositories can take to increase dataset FAIRness for non-researcher use cases.

Citation: Gee, B. M. 2025. Building a bigger tent: institutional tracking of data publications and maximally FAIR data require rigorous repository metadata standards. MorphoBank Connects: virtual, September 18–19, 2025.

Fluctuating Asymmetry Reveals Species-Specific and Metapopulation Responses to Anthropization in Squamates

Aldo Gómez-Benitez*, Erika A. Reyes-Velázquez, Carlos A. Mastachi-Loza, Jose F. Méndez-Sánchez, Justin L. Rheubert, Oswaldo Hernández-Gallegos

*gobeal940814@gmail.com

Keywords: Fluctuating asymmetry; Anthropization; Squamates; Developmental instability; Life history traits

Anthropization, through habitat fragmentation and land-use change, is a key driver of biodiversity loss, especially in megadiverse countries like Mexico. Detecting early signs of stress in wildlife is critical for conservation. Fluctuating asymmetry (FA), a deviation from perfect bilateral symmetry, is a sensitive indicator of developmental instability induced by environmental stress. We used geometric morphometrics to assess FA in five sympatric squamate species inhabiting an anthropized landscape in El Cerrillo Piedras Blancas, State of Mexico: *Barisia imbricata*, *Sceloporus grammicus*, *Crotalus triseriatus*, *Thamnophis eques*, and *Thamnophis scalaris*. Standardized photographs of dorsal head views were analyzed using 22 anatomical landmarks. Procrustes ANOVA was used to test for FA; Mahalanobis distances quantified asymmetry magnitude and were compared to centroid size to test for compensatory growth. Additionally, we calculated the Jacobian expansion factor to localize shape changes and constructed a predictive CART model relating FA to environmental variables extracted from satellite imagery. Three species (*B. imbricata*, *T. eques*, and *T. scalaris*) showed significant FA, with no consistent relationship between asymmetry and size, suggesting limited compensatory development. Jacobian maps indicated localized shape instability rather than organism-wide asymmetry. The predictive model explained 30% of the variance in FA and identified key environmental stressors, such as vegetation loss and proximity to agricultural areas. Our results highlight the value of FA as a non-invasive early warning signal of anthropogenic stress in 4 reptiles. This approach enables rapid field assessments and may inform management strategies in protected areas, urban–wildland interfaces, and other vulnerable landscapes.

Citation: Gómez-Benitez, A, E. A. Reyes-Velázquez, C. A. Mastachi-Loza, J. F. Méndez-Sánchez, J. L. Rheubert, and O. Hernández-Gallegos. 2025. Fluctuating Asymmetry Reveals Species-Specific and Metapopulation Responses to Anthropization in Squamates. MorphoBank Connects: virtual, September 18-19, 2025.

Accelerating FAIR Morphological Data Curation with an AI-Empowered Tool

Shreya Jariwala^{1,2*}

¹Phoenix Bioinformatics, CA, USA

²University of California, Berkeley, CA, USA

*sjariwala@morphobank.org

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Phylogenetics, Data Curation

Curation of morphological datasets, especially those derived from paleontological studies is often a slow, manual process prone to formatting inconsistencies and typographical errors. These issues present major barriers to achieving compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles and reduce the utility of such datasets in large-scale evolutionary and taxonomic research. To address this, we developed an AI-assisted curation pipeline for Morphobank, a collaborative, open-access repository for morphological phylogenetic matrices. This tool automates the extraction, standardization, and integration of morphological character names and states into NEXUS files from published literature. The system utilizes PymuPDF, a tool to make structured text extractions and pre-processing of PDF documents easier. It then removes extraneous content such as references, figures, and parts of the paper that aren't the character list. It then employs Gemini, a large language model, to identify and generate structured morphological character data. These outputs are formatted into a JSON schema and reintegrated into incomplete NEXUS files, improving completeness and dataset interoperability. This approach has been deployed in a large-scale data migration project transferring over 300 matrices from the Paleobiology Database (PBDB) to MorphoBank, significantly reducing manual workload while maintaining high accuracy in character-state extraction. By automating key components of the curation workflow, our AI-based system enhances data quality, accelerates repository integration, and enables broader reuse of legacy phylogenetic datasets. This work demonstrates the potential of AI to support sustainable and scalable data curation practices across paleontology and systematics, paving the way for more reproducible and accessible evolutionary research.

Citation: Jariwala, S., B. L. Long-Fox, and T. Z. Berardini. 2025. Accelerating FAIR Morphological Data Curation with an AI-Empowered Tool. MorphoBank Connects: virtual, September 18-19, 2025.

Is morphology still relevant to phylogenetic analyses?

Daniel Yudi Miyahara Nakamura*, Ward Wheeler, Taran Grant

*dani_ymn@usp.br

Keywords: morphology, phenomics, total evidence, parsimony, MKv models

Phylogenetic analyses of extant taxa have relied mostly on DNA sequences. The proportion of phenomic characters relative to molecular characters has been reduced with the advent of massive parallel DNA sequencing. However, phenomic evidence enables sampling more characters and taxa without molecular data (such as fossils). Here we tested the impact of phenomic evidence on topology and support values using a total evidence approach. We quantitatively assessed five aspects of the impact of phenomics using 58 empirical data sets. First, our results demonstrated that the addition of phenomic evidence changed 90.3% (47/52) of topologies. Second, incongruences between molecular and total evidence trees are correlated with the proportion of phenomic evidence ($P < 0.05$). Third, the addition of phenomic evidence is more impactful on parsimony than maximum likelihood analyses according to Cluster Information distances ($P < 0.05$). Fourth, the addition of phenomic evidence can either reduce or increase bootstrap values. Fifth, bootstrap values from molecular clades are able to predict the occurrence of total evidence clades in most cases. However, in a few exceptions, molecular clades with 100% bootstrap values can be absent in total evidence trees. Thus, the monophyly of total evidence groups is not completely predictable based on molecular-only data. Overall, our findings strengths that phenomic evidence still matters in phylogenetic systematics.

Citation: Miyahara Nakamura, D. Y., W. Wheeler, and T. Grant. 2025. Is morphology still relevant to phylogenetic analyses? MorphoBank Connects: virtual, September 18–19, 2025.

Repository of morphological data for deep-sea faunal novelties

Xikun Song^{1*}

¹Institute of Deep-sea Science and Engineering, Chinese Academy of Sciences

*xksong@idsse.ac.cn

Keywords: morphological data; deep-sea; fauna

MorphoBank has become my first choice for depositing morphological data associated with scientific publications. In this brief talk, I will share my experience using MorphoBank to archive morphological datasets from five published projects (P3629, P3801, P3840, P4108, P4854) and one unpublished project under consideration. The focus will be on the repository of morphological data for deep-sea and hadal faunal novelties. I will also discuss some experiences I encountered during the submission and peer review process.

Citation: Song, X. 2025. Repository of morphological data for deep-sea faunal novelties. MorphoBank Connects: virtual, September 18-19, 2025.

Quantitative analysis of ophiomicrodermatoglyphics in shed-off skin: a novel taxonomic approach in snake identification

Harij Uddin^{1*}, Md. Habib Ullah¹, Najmul Hasan¹, Aniruddha Ghose²,
Mohammad Abdul Wahed Chowdhury^{1,2}, Ibrahim Khalil Al Haidar^{1,2}

¹University of Chittagong, Bangladesh

²Chittagong Medical College, Bangladesh

*harijuddin11@gmail.com

Keywords: Cobras, ecdysis, microdermatoglyphics, species differentiation, non-invasive method, snake taxonomy

Proper snake identification is essential for ecological research, conservation, and snakebite management, especially regarding venomous species. However, Traditional morphological methods pose envenomation risks during live handling, while molecular approaches require specialized equipment and expertise, limiting their practicality and emphasize the need for safer, more accessible alternatives. This study introduces a novel, non-invasive identification method using microdermatoglyphic features from shed-off snake skin. We examined six microdermatoglyphic characters from fifteen representative scales from the head, body and tail region of *Naja kaouthia* and *Naja naja*. Statistical analyses revealed that these features can reliably distinguish the two species and also differentiate between sexes. Among the characters, edge widest part distance (edge_wpd) was the most discriminative, significantly ($p < 0.001$) separating 93.33% of the studied scales, followed by edge_area (86.67%) and number of follicles per 20,000 μm^2 (46.67%). Microdermatoglyphic characters also significantly ($p < 0.001$) differentiated males and females in both *Naja kaouthia* and *Naja naja*, with edge_area being the most effective character distinguishing 60% of scales in *N. kaouthia* and 20% in *N. naja*, followed by number of follicles per 20,000 μm^2 (folli_20_thou), which differentiated 33% of scales in *N. kaouthia* and 13% in *N. naja*. This non-invasive approach to snake identification provides biologists a promising tool for snake taxonomy that will help better study biodiversity.

Citation: Uddin, H., M. H. Ullah, N. Hasan, A. Ghose, M. A. W. Chowdhury, and I. K. A. Haidar. 2025. Quantitative analysis of ophiomicrodermatoglyphics in shed-off skin: a novel taxonomic approach in snake identification. MorphoBank Connects: virtual, September 18–19, 2025.

Making academic publishing Open and FAIR: how MorphoBank aids data reproducibility

Mark T. Young^{1-3*}

¹ School of Biological Sciences, University of Southampton, Southampton, United Kingdom; ² School of GeoSciences, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, United Kingdom; ³LWL-Museum für Naturkunde, Münster, Germany; ⁴ Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom; ⁵ Department of Anatomy, New York Institute of Technology College of Osteopathic Medicine, Old Westbury, NY, USA; ⁶ Department of Paleontology, University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland; ⁷ Department of Geosciences, Auburn University, Auburn, Alabama 36849, USA; ⁸ Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Departamento de Biología Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales, Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata, B7602AYL Mar del Plata, Argentina; ⁹ Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont (ICP-CERCA), Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain; ¹⁰ School of Earth Sciences, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK; ¹² Grupo Aragosaurus-IUCA, Paleontología, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain; ¹³ Jackson School of Geosciences, The University of Texas at Austin, USA; ¹⁴ Department of Biosciences, Swansea University, Swansea, United Kingdom; ¹⁵ Department of Earth Sciences, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB2 3EQ, United Kingdom; ¹⁶ Museum of Zoology, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB2 3EJ, United Kingdom; ¹⁷ Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), División Paleontología Vertebrados, Facultad de Ciencias Naturales y Museo, Universidad Nacional de la Plata, Paseo del Bosque s/n, B1900FWA, Argentina; ¹⁸ School of Geography and Planning, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou 510006, China; ¹⁹ Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI 48109, USA; ²⁰ Museum of Paleontology, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI 48109, USA; ²¹ Department of Organismic and Evolutionary Biology, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA 02138, USA; ²² Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA 02138, USA; ²³ Turkana Basin Institute, Nairobi, Kenya; ²⁴ Departamento de Paleobiología, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales – CSIC, C/ José Gutiérrez Abascal 2, Madrid 28006, Spain; ²⁵ National Museum of Natural History, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine; ²⁶ University of Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland; ²⁷ MorphoBank, Phoenix Bioinformatics, Newark, CA, USA; ²⁸ Department of Chemistry, Biology, and Health Sciences, South Dakota School of Mines and Technology, Rapid City, SD, USA; ²⁹ Philadelphia College of Osteopathic Medicine – Georgia Campus, Suwanee, GA 30024, USA; ³⁰ Department of Environmental Biology, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy; ³¹ Universidade Federal de Santa Maria, São João do Polêsine, Brazil; ³³ Institut Català de Paleoecologia Humana i Evolució Social (IPHES-CERCA), Tarragona, Spain; ³⁴ Millennium

Nucleus Early Evolutionary Transitions of Mammals, Santiago, Chile; ³⁵ Senckenberg Research Institute and Natural History Museum, Frankfurt am Main, 60325, Germany; ³⁶ Max Planck Institute of Geoanthropology, Jena, Germany; ³⁷ Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution, Griffith University, Nathan, Queensland, Australia; ³⁸ Department of Life Sciences, University of Lincoln, Lincoln, UK; ³⁹ Institute of Rock Structure and Mechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic; ⁴⁰ National Library of Technology, Prague, Czech Republic; ⁴¹ Franklin and Marshall College, Lancaster, PA, USA; ⁴² Universidad Tecnológica Nacional, Facultad Regional San Rafael, Instituto de Evolución, Ecología Histórica y Ambiente (IDEVEA), San Rafael, Argentina; ⁴⁴ Department of Science and Mathematics, Mount Aloysius College, Cresson, USA; ⁴⁵ Section of Vertebrate Paleontology, Carnegie Museum of Natural History, Pittsburgh, USA; ⁴⁶ School of Resources and Environment, Henan Polytechnic University, Jiaozuo 454003, China

* marktyoung1984@gmail.com

‡ All other co-authors are listed in alphabetical order

Keywords: Academic publishing; FAIR principles; Open Science; Phylogenetics; Registered Reports; Reproducibility

The Open Science movement aims to make scientific research more transparent and accessible. Given the reproducibility crises and global inequity of data access, Open Science principles are more important than ever. Within an academic publishing setting, the Open Science framework makes the publication process more transparent and trustworthy, and normalises the sharing of data. We, the editorial board of the journal *Historical Biology*, are committed to Open Science and FAIR principles. *Historical Biology* is a hybrid open-access journal that publishes papers covering evolutionary and systematic biology through time, spanning both archaeology and palaeontology, and clades across the entire tree of life. We have recently undertaken a number of changes to refocus the journal, and as part of our commitment to Open and FAIR principles, we: 1) have introduced dedicated article types such as ‘Data Note’, ‘Method’, and ‘Registered Reports’; 2) are now a PCI RR-Friendly journal; and 3) have introduced dedicated editorial roles (including a Data Editor and Phylogenetics Editor). These new editorial roles strengthen our ability to support authors in making their research reproducible and replicable, both by ensuring datasets are properly managed and that manuscripts adhere to Open Science practices, including pre-registration and the use of online repositories like MorphoBank. Moving forward, MorphoBank will be our recommended repository for phylogenetic datasets, particularly from 2026 when our data sharing policy shifts to ‘Openly Available’. By promoting best practices for data management and collaboration with authors, *Historical Biology* aims to contribute to a more transparent and accessible scientific community.

Citation: Young, M. T., N. F. Adams, B. Beatty, J. Bestwick, M. S. Bhat, J. Bodnar, A. Bolet, S. L. Brusatte, D. Castanera, J. Clarke, J. A. Cooper, D. J. Field, S. Gouiric-Cavalli, H. Huang, R. J. Knecht, F. Knoll, O. Kovalchuk, B. L. Long-Fox, R. K. McAfee, B. Mecozzi, R. T. Müller, D. Naish, A. Pineda, H. P. Püschel, R. Racicot, J. Ristevski, S. L. Shelley, L. Šmídová, R. D. K. Thomas, V. V. Vennari, A. Villa, J. A. Whitlock, and L.-J. Zhang. 2025. Making academic publishing Open and FAIR: how MorphoBank aids data reproducibility. *MorphoBank Connects: virtual*, September 18–19, 2025.